

Grey Wolf Optimisation of an Operating Strategy for Energy Storage Systems in Electrically Driven Railway Vehicles

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Abstract—This paper presents an energy optimal operating strategy for the utilisation of energy storage systems (ESS) in electrically driven railway vehicles. First, a detailed simulation model of the complete power train of a generic railway vehicle, supplied by an electric energy source, is described. The presented operating strategy comprises the power management between the two power sources of the vehicle, namely the catenary as well as the ESS. To derive the energy optimal parametrisation for the proposed power management approach, a Grey Wolf Optimiser (GWO) is applied, which is inspired by the hunting behavior of grey wolves in nature.

I. INTRODUCTION

The utilisation of electric energy within the railway sector is a significant step toward a reduction of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions in the transport sector. In 2015, the share of electrified tracks within Europe attained more than 60% of the total track length of the railway sector, see [2]. Within the last years, the implementation of electric storage systems (ESS) like batteries is common for diesel trains – resulting in hybrid railway vehicles that allow for a recuperation of the braking energy. For hybrid concepts involving an internal combustion engine, several energy optimal operating strategies were investigated during the last years, e.g. in [3], [4], and [5].

The implementation of ESS in electric trains offers the possibility to operate electric trains on non-electrified tracks. This enables an operation of electric trains even in regions, where an electric power supply is either not available or an installation would be too expensive.

The current paper, however, focuses on the ESS power management for the utilisation of ESS on electrified tracks. Here, there are two possibilities to recuperate the braking energy and to employ the traction energy: The external energy source (e.g. catenary or power rail) and the ESS. This additional degree of freedom for the power management will be used for the implementation of an energy-optimised operation. In this case, the term ‘energy optimised operation’ does not only focus on energy savings but also on an optimisation of the power characteristic at the external energy source, e.g. a reduction of power peaks at the catenary.

The basic property that is exploited for the ESS power management is the difference in the cycle efficiencies of the two different branches displayed in Fig. 1.

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Fig. 1. Cycle efficiencies of ESS branch and catenary branch.

The first branch, cycle I in Fig. 1, covers the components between the DC intermediate circuit and the catenary, whereas the second branch, cycle II in Fig. 1, includes the components of the ESS branch. The cycle efficiency of the single branches consists of the serially coupled efficiencies of the single components and covers the recuperation of energy as well as a positive power flow, used for traction. Therefore, the total cycle efficiency for one branch is given by

$$\eta_{cycle}^{\chi} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_c^{\chi}} \eta_i^{\text{traction}} + \sum_{i=1}^{n_c^{\chi}} \eta_i^{\text{recuperation}}, \quad (1)$$

where $n_c^{\chi}, \chi \in \{bat, cat\}$ is equal to the number of components per battery/catenary branch.

The simulation model to evaluate the efficiencies of the branches as well as of the single components is presented in Section II. An operating strategy approach for the application of the ESS is developed within Section III. For the energy optimal parametrisation of the operating strategy, a Grey Wolf Optimisation (GWO) is employed. This specific particle swarm optimisation method is inspired by the hunting behavior of grey wolves in nature. The GWO algorithm was first described in [6] and served as a basis for several extensions and modifications, which are summarized within [7]. In Section IV, the GWO algorithm is summarized briefly. The simulation results are presented and discussed within Section V. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper and gives an outlook on further work.

II. SIMULATION MODEL

This section presents the implemented simulation model of the traction chain, which is the basis for the calculation of the total energy consumption of the train. The considered traction topology, depicted in Fig. 2, is generic for a modern railway vehicle that is connected to an AC power supply.

Fig. 2. Traction topology in backward simulation mode.

A. Simulation Model of the Traction Chain

To achieve a realistic calculation of the energy consumption of the total traction chain, it is advantageous to implement a backward simulation, see [8]. The backward simulation is based on a block structure that corresponds to the reverse direction of the physical power flow. Accordingly, the desired output for the backward simulation is given by a fixed velocity profile. Then, the corresponding inputs signals follow from the inverse dynamics represented by the backward simulation topology. From a control point of view, this is equivalent to a flatness-based approach and the solution of an inverse problem. The desired velocity profile meets all the constraints given by a timetable and is calculated in a separate trajectory planning module. There are several methods to determine such velocity trajectories, e.g. [9], [10] and [11].

The mechanical behavior of the vehicle is governed by

$$k_{rot}M\dot{v} = F_{wheel} - F_{res} - F_{inc}. \quad (2)$$

Here, M denotes the total mass of the vehicle, k_{rot} a factor to account for the additional rotary masses, F_{wheel} the force at the wheel and \dot{v} the resulting acceleration of the vehicle. A common approach to determine the driving resistances F_{res} is the Davis equation

$$F_{res} = c_0 + c_1v + c_2v^2, \quad (3)$$

which involves three coefficients (c_0, c_1, c_2) for describing the overall resistance as a function of the vehicle speed $v(t)$. The inclination γ defines the inclination force

$$F_{inc} = M\sin(\gamma)g. \quad (4)$$

The requirement to track a desired velocity profile, in compliance with the mechanical properties of the vehicle, leads to a total power request P_{wheel} at the wheel. The energy losses of the included electric traction components (motor, motor converter, absorption circuit, line converter, transformer, auxiliary converter, ESS converter) are determined via the evaluation of efficiency maps. The efficiency map for the i -th component is implemented either as a function of the current load power, i.e., $\eta_i = f(P_{load,i})$ (e.g. for the transformer), or in dependence on both load power and angular velocity, i.e., $\eta_i = f(P_{load,i}, \omega_i)$ (e.g. for the electric motor), see Fig. 3.

(a) Efficiency maps as a function of (b) Efficiency curve in dependence of load and angular velocity.

Fig. 3. Implementation of the efficiency maps.

B. Simulation Model of the Auxiliaries

Beside the energy losses produced by the traction components, the simulation structure also considers the power P_{aux} for several auxiliaries. As presented in Fig. 4, the electric auxiliaries involve two contributions: The first one covers auxiliaries that are considered as constant over the duration of the drive cycle, e.g. light and HVAC systems.

Fig. 4. Electric auxiliaries consisting of constant auxiliaries and requested cooling power.

This constant auxiliary power $P_{aux,const}$ may be adapted regarding the implemented train service or season. The second term stands for the cooling amount $P_{cool,i}$ for every single traction component. This cooling power $P_{cool,i}$ of the i -th traction component is implemented as a function of the component load $P_{cool,i} = f(P_{load,i})$. As a result, the total cooling power request of the traction chain is defined by

$$P_{cool} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_c} P_{cool,i}, \quad (5)$$

where n_c represents the number of components within the traction chain. As presented in Fig. 4, the total auxiliary power is given by

$$P_{aux}(t) = P_{aux,const} + P_{cool}(t). \quad (6)$$

C. Simulation Model of the ESS

To describe the behavior of the ESS, a corresponding electrical circuit of the ESS is depicted in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Electric circuit model of the ESS.

With a given open-circuit voltage V_{OC} and an internal resistance R_{ESS} , the current I_{ESS} charging/discharging the ESS is

governed by

$$I_{ESS}(t) = \frac{V_{OC}(t) - \sqrt{V_{OC}(t)^2 - 4P_{ESS}(t)R_{ESS}}}{2R_{ESS}}. \quad (7)$$

Here, $P_{ESS}(t)$ represents the power profile at the ESS. As a result, the state of charge follows from

$$SoC(t) = SoC(t_0) - \frac{1}{C_{ESS}} \int_0^t I_{ESS}(\tau) d\tau. \quad (8)$$

Here, $SoC(t_0)$ is the state of charge at the beginning of the drive cycle, and C_{ESS} represents the capacity of the ESS.

The power P_{ESS} depends on the operating strategy of the specific ESS application, which is presented in the next section.

III. ENERGY OPTIMAL OPERATING STRATEGY FOR THE ESS

The operating strategy for the energy management of the ESS adjusts the power flow at the DC intermediate circuit of the train. The total power at the intermediate circuit P_{DC} represents the sum of the required traction power P_{trac} and the auxiliary power P_{DCaux} at the DC link. Accordingly, the power at the DC link is given by

$$P_{DC} = P_{trac} + P_{DCaux}, \quad (9)$$

where for $P_{DC} < 0$ power is recuperated, whereas in the case of $P_{DC} > 0$ power is used for traction.

The main objective of the ESS energy management is a favorable separation of the power flow at the DC circuit between the ESS and the external energy source (catenary, power rail). All possible power flows are depicted in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Operating strategy for the ESS.

To parametrise the operating strategy, the ESS strategy parameters

$$\underline{\epsilon} = [\epsilon_{trac} \quad \epsilon_{aux} \quad \epsilon_{rec}]^T \quad (10)$$

are introduced. Here, the factor ϵ_{trac} defines the power split of the traction power, whereas the factor ϵ_{aux} determines the split of auxiliary power. Another factor – regarding the power split during recuperation – is denoted by ϵ_{rec} .

Based on these ESS strategy parameters, the power flow from the ESS supplying the traction process is given by

$$P_{ESS,trac} = \epsilon_{trac} P_{DC}. \quad (11)$$

The amount of auxiliary power that is taken from the ESS becomes

$$P_{ESS,aux} = \epsilon_{aux} P_{DC}. \quad (12)$$

The remaining power required during traction mode results in

$$P_{cat,trac} = (1 - (\epsilon_{aux} + \epsilon_{trac})) P_{DC}. \quad (13)$$

For the recuperation mode, the amount of power for the ESS is given by

$$P_{ESS,rec} = \epsilon_{rec} P_{DC}, \quad (14)$$

whereas the recuperation power to the catenary reads

$$P_{cat,rec} = (1 - \epsilon_{rec}) P_{DC}. \quad (15)$$

The cost function J for the energy-optimal operating strategy is formulated as

$$J = E_{Net} + \alpha_{SoC} (SoC(t_0) - SoC(t_f))^2. \quad (16)$$

Here, E_{net} represents the total net energy at the end of the drive cycle ($E_{net} = E_{trac} - E_{rec}$). E_{trac} stands for the consumed energy and E_{rec} for the recuperated one, which are determined by the simulated traction chain as described in Sect. II. Additionally, the cost function includes a penalty term – in the form of a weighted squared deviation of the final ESS state of charge. Here, $SoC(t_0)$ and $SoC(t_f)$ denote the state of charge at the beginning and at the end of the drive cycle, and α_{SoC} serves as a weighting factor. This allows for both a balanced SoC at the beginning and the end of the drive cycle and avoids an additional charging or discharging at the terminal station.

The parameters $\underline{\epsilon}^*$ represent the solution of the optimisation problem, and are determined by minimising the cost function

$$\underline{\epsilon}^* = \arg \left(\min_{\underline{\epsilon}} \{J(\underline{\epsilon})\} \right). \quad (17)$$

To solve the optimisation problem denoted in (17), a gradient-free optimiser is applied, which is presented in the following section.

IV. GREY WOLF OPTIMISATION

As it is not possible to analytically derive gradient information of the cost function defined in (16), a gradient-free optimisation approach is employed. Therefore, the chosen particle optimiser, which operates without analytical gradient information, is presented in the sequel.

The Grey Wolf Optimisation (GWO) approach belongs to the class of particle swarm optimisation, and is inspired by the hunting behavior of grey wolves in nature, see [6] and [7].

To explain the specific behavior of this particle swarm optimisation, the particles (possible solution candidates) are denoted as wolves, and the total set of particles is called pack. The progress of the set of particles (the pack) is influenced by the position of the three leading wolves, here denoted as α -, β - and δ -wolves. The remaining candidates belong to a group of ω -wolves.

The vector $\underline{\varepsilon}_k^j$ of the optimisation parameters contains the position of the j -th particle for the k -th iteration. Moreover, the position of the prey is represented by the optimal solution $\underline{\varepsilon}^*$. The general update for the particle positions is given by

$$\underline{\varepsilon}_{k+1} = \underline{\varepsilon}_k - \underline{A}_k \underline{d}_k, \quad (18)$$

where the distance to the estimated optimal solution \underline{d}_k follows from

$$\underline{d}_k = |\underline{C}_k \underline{\varepsilon}_k^* - \underline{\varepsilon}_k|. \quad (19)$$

Here, the matrices $\underline{A}_k = \text{diag}\{a_{i,k}\}$ and $\underline{C}_k = \text{diag}\{c_{i,k}\}$ contain random scaling coefficients

$$a_{i,k} = 2 \cdot \alpha(k) \cdot r_{1,k} - \alpha(k) \quad (20)$$

and

$$c_{i,k} = 2 \cdot r_{2,k}, \quad (21)$$

with random variables $r_1, r_2 \in [0, 1]$, $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. The number of optimisation parameters is given by n (here: $n = 3 = \dim\{\underline{\varepsilon}\}$). The function $\alpha(k)$ serves as a weighting function to reduce the individual motion of the single particles over the iteration process. As a default setting, the function is chosen as

$$\alpha(k) = 2 - \frac{2k}{k_{max}}, \quad (22)$$

which corresponds to a linear decrease from 2 to 0. Here, k_{max} defines the maximum number of iterations.

To determine the fitness of the single particles, the cost function

$$J_k^j = f(\underline{\varepsilon}_k^j) \quad (23)$$

defined in (16) is evaluated for every particle position $\underline{\varepsilon}_k^j$. Subsequently, the first three fittest solutions are determined to characterise the positions $\underline{\varepsilon}_\alpha$, $\underline{\varepsilon}_\beta$ and $\underline{\varepsilon}_\delta$ of the three leading wolves. As only an estimate for the position of the prey is available, the position update of the pack is based on the position of the leading wolves. Consequently, the position update for the j -th wolf becomes

$$\underline{\varepsilon}_{k+1}^j = \frac{\underline{\varepsilon}_{1,k}^j + \underline{\varepsilon}_{2,k}^j + \underline{\varepsilon}_{3,k}^j}{3}, \quad (24)$$

with

$$\underline{\varepsilon}_{1,k}^j = \underline{\varepsilon}_{\alpha,k} - \underline{A}_{1,k} \underline{d}_{\alpha,k}^j, \quad (25)$$

$$\underline{\varepsilon}_{2,k}^j = \underline{\varepsilon}_{\beta,k} - \underline{A}_{2,k} \underline{d}_{\beta,k}^j, \quad (26)$$

$$\underline{\varepsilon}_{3,k}^j = \underline{\varepsilon}_{\delta,k} - \underline{A}_{3,k} \underline{d}_{\delta,k}^j, \quad (27)$$

defining randomly distributed positions around the α -, β - and δ -wolves. The distances \underline{d}_k^j between the current particle and the leading wolves are denoted by

$$\underline{d}_{\alpha,k}^j = \underline{C}_{1,k} \underline{\varepsilon}_{\alpha,k}^j - \underline{\varepsilon}_k^j, \quad (28)$$

$$\underline{d}_{\beta,k}^j = \underline{C}_{2,k} \underline{\varepsilon}_{\beta,k}^j - \underline{\varepsilon}_k^j, \quad (29)$$

$$\underline{d}_{\delta,k}^j = \underline{C}_{3,k} \underline{\varepsilon}_{\delta,k}^j - \underline{\varepsilon}_k^j. \quad (30)$$

Fig. 7. Position update in GWO according to [6].

The total position update is illustrated in Fig. 7.

As the random values for \underline{A}_k and \underline{C}_k characterise the position update for the pack. They are the main parameters adjusting the exploration and exploitation behavior of the GWO approach. According to (20), the matrix entries $a_{i,k}$ of \underline{A}_k vary in the range of $[-2, 2]$. Here, $|a_i| > 1$ is characteristic for exploration to ensure a global search, whereas $|a_i| < 1$ leads to exploitation to increase the accuracy of the solution. Applied to the presented approach it can be concluded: With the linear function $\alpha(k)$ defined in (22), there is no possibility for an exploration for $k \geq \frac{k_{max}}{2}$. To adjust the exploration/exploitation behavior, also nonlinear dependencies $\alpha(k)$ may be implemented, see [12] and [13].

V. SIMULATION RESULTS AND ASSESSMENT

The main objective of the current section is the presentation of simulation results using the ESS operating strategy, determined by the GWO. To investigate and clarify the potential of the ESS application, various scenarios are evaluated and compared.

A. Scenario Description

All the presented scenarios are subjected to the same driving cycle, which is characterised by a given velocity profile $v(t)$ and an altitude profile $h(t)$. This underlying driving cycle as well as the resulting power profile at the wheel $P_{wheel}(t)$ are shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Velocity and altitude profiles of the considered drive cycle.

The presented velocity profile between two stops is composed of four driving states, namely:

- acceleration (with maximum traction effort)
- cruising (with constant speed)
- coasting (no traction power at the wheels)
- braking (with maximum braking effort)

The additional mass of the ESS is accounted for trajectory planning because it has a major effect on both the maximum acceleration and the braking effort of the train. As a result, the power profile at the wheel also differs from the baseline power profile. As the deviations are negligible, the adjusted velocity profile and the appropriate power profile at the wheel are not depicted; nevertheless, they are employed in the simulations accordingly.

The benchmark scenario (Scenario I) presents a default traction chain without an ESS. The four other scenarios consider an implementation of the ESS for various applications. Scenario II addresses an ESS within the default traction chain, whereas two other scenarios correspond to the simulation results for an increased component efficiency in either the ESS branch or in the catenary branch, see Fig. 1. For scenario III and IV, the efficiency of the ESS converter and the one of the line converter, see Fig. 2, are increased by $\Delta\eta = 1\%$ to show the influence of different cycle efficiencies on the ESS operating strategy. Scenario V deals with an approach where the maximum recuperation effort is required. Therefore, the recuperation factor ϵ_{rec} is fixed to 100%. The presented scenarios are summarized within Table I.

Scenario	Short Description
I	No ESS, default traction chain
II	ESS included, default traction chain
III	ESS included, traction chain with increased efficiency in the battery branch ($\eta_{lc}^{III} = \eta_{lc}^{BASE} + 1\%$)*
IV	ESS included, traction chain with increased efficiency in the catenary branch ($\eta_{ESSC}^{IV} = \eta_{ESSC}^{BASE} + 1\%$ **)
V	ESS included, default traction chain, maximum recuperation is required ($\epsilon_{rec}^V = 100\%$)

* lc : line converter, ** $ESSC$: ESS converter

TABLE I
SIMULATION SCENARIOS

B. Simulation Results

The GWO is applied to each of the presented scenarios. The determined ESS strategy parameters are summarised in Table II. It shows for scenario II that it is possible to obtain an energy saving by using the ESS – despite the additional mass for the ESS components. To enable a fair comparison, it is worth pointing out that components with increased efficiencies are employed within scenarios III and IV, which also causes an improvement regarding the energy budget. The operation parameters for scenario V lead to a slightly higher

energy usage in comparison to the baseline. However, this application scenario also implicates some advantages, which are described below in detail.

Scenario	I	II	III	IV	V
Traction energy amount ϵ_{trac}^* in %	-	1.9	2.4	0.4	0.5
Auxiliary energy amount ϵ_{aux}^* in %	-	6	6	18	82
Recuperation factor ϵ_{rec}^* in %	-	28	33	16.5	100
Net energy in kWh	5255	5242	5238	5187	5280

TABLE II
OPTIMAL PARAMETERS FOR THE ESS OPERATING STRATEGY.

Given the defined traction topology, the ratio between the requested traction energy at the DC link E_{trac} and the auxiliary energy at the DC link E_{DCaux} is about

$$E_{trac} \approx 10 \cdot E_{DCaux}. \quad (31)$$

Therefore, the values for the amount of traction energy are comparatively low regarding the amount of auxiliary power supplied by the ESS.

The determined recuperation factor ϵ_{rec}^* allows for an interpretation of the overall energy turnover of the battery. As the SoC of the battery is balanced over the drive cycle and the battery size is identical for all scenarios, a larger recuperation factor ϵ_{rec} corresponds to a more intense usage of the ESS. Here, it becomes obvious that the different cycle efficiencies of scenarios III and IV influence the usage of the ESS. While the recuperation factor is increased for scenario III due to the increased efficiency of the ESS converter, the recuperation factor decreases if a larger efficiency is employed in the catenary branch (scenario IV).

The intensity of the ESS usage is reflected also in the state-of-charge characteristic, see Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. State-of-charge characteristic for the different application scenarios.

The minimum depth of discharge is achieved in scenario IV, which is characterized by the lowest recuperation factor. However, scenario V shows the highest SoC variation. Here, the ESS is discharged/charged up to the minimum/maximum

SoC value. This effect is caused by the fixed recuperation factor of $\epsilon_{rec}^V = 100\%$. In this scenario, the full potential of the battery can not be utilized – especially, in the long recuperation phase during the downhill section –, which leads to the comparatively highest energy usage of all of the presented scenarios. This effect is underlined by the presented power characteristics shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10. Power characteristic at the ESS.

For the scenarios II, III and IV, the ESS is capable of supplying the traction chain with traction energy during the uphill section ($t \approx 5750s \dots 8200s$) and of covering part of the recuperated power during the downhill section ($t \approx 8550s \dots 9600s$). For scenario V, however, this is not ensured because the ESS attains its SoC limits.

Nevertheless, the positive effect of applying scenario V becomes visible in Fig. 11: The application of the ESS leads to reduced peaks in the power characteristic of the catenary. This effect is most pronounced for scenario V, as long as the ESS is not charged/discharged up to a SoC limit, see the zoomed detail in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Power characteristic at the catenary.

This reduction of power peaks at the catenary contributes significantly to the receptivity of the network, see [14]. Another ESS application approach that focuses on a peak shaving approach for DC railway systems is presented in [15].

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK ON FUTURE RESEARCH

In this paper, an optimisation of the ESS operating strategy for the on-board application in electric driven railway vehi-

cles is presented. To determine optimal parameters regarding the energy-optimal ESS operation, a Grey Wolf Optimiser is employed. This GWO exploits a detailed simulation model of the traction chain topology to determine the energy usage of the vehicle. For a comparative analysis of the results, the optimisation algorithm is applied to different application scenarios. The corresponding simulation results are subject to a specified test case and will differ for different drive cycles or traction chain characteristics.

On the one hand, future research will focus on a modification of the GWO algorithm using alternative subsidy functions $\alpha(k)$ or an extended hierarchy structure (e.g. more than one α -, β -, δ -wolf).

On the other hand, the optimisation will be applied on further operating scenarios like an ESS supply for non-electrified parts of the tracks, an intermediate ESS charging at the substations or a different selection of the cost function (16). Thereby, different optimisation characteristics can be implemented, e.g., power peak shaving.

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